

MADANIY XABARDORLIKNI OSHIRISH VA EKOLOGIK BARQAROR TURIZMNI RIVOJLANTIRISH | xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy anjuman

YASHIL IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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Yashil

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«Og‘ir ekologik sharoitga qaramasdan, mamlakatimiz taraqqiyotiga munosib hissa qo‘shib kelayotgan Qoraqalpog‘iston Respublikasini, uning barcha shahar, tuman va ovullarini kompleks tarzda rivojlantirish, mehnatkash va matonatli, oqko‘ngil va bag‘rikeng qoraqalpoq elining hayotini obod va farovon etishga har qachongidan ham ustuvor ahamiyat qaratamiz.

Bizning oliy va ezgu maqsadimiz – birgalikdagi fidokorona mehnatimiz bilan Yangi O‘zbekiston tarkibida Yangi Qoraqalpog‘istonni bunyod etishdir.»

Sh.M.MIRZIYOYEV
O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti

Prezident: “Bu ko‘prik o‘zbek va qoraqalpoq xalqlari o‘rtasidagi og‘zibirlik va hamkorlik ko‘prigidir”.

Qoraqalpog‘iston Respublikasini Xorazm viloyati bilan bog‘lovchi ko‘prik. Asosiy qo‘shma ko‘prikning uzunligi 413 metr bo‘lib, eni 8 metr; har bir oraliq‘i 66 metrni tashkil qiladi. Uning 7 ta ustuni 6 ta oraliqqa o‘rnatilgan.

KIRISH

2024-yilning 17–18-may kunlari Qoraqalpog‘iston Respublikasi Xo‘jayli tumanida o‘tkazilgan «Madaniy xabardorlikni oshirish va ekologik barqaror turizmni rivojlantirish» mavzusidagi xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy anjuman Qoraqalpog‘istonning boy madaniy, etnografik va ekologik merosini keng jamoatchilikka tanitishda hamda turizm infratuzilmalarini mustahkamlashda muhim qadam bo‘ldi

Anjumanning asosiy maqsadi Qoraqalpog‘istonda turizm salohiyatini jahon turizm bozoriga olib kirish va madaniy xabardorlikni oshirishdir. Qoraqalpog‘iston o‘zining tarixiy boyliklari, arxeologik yodgorliklari va o‘ziga xos tabiiy manzaralari bilan dunyo sayyohlarini jalb etadigan katta jozibadorlikka ega. Bu hududda jahon madaniy va tabiiy merosi obyektlariga mansub ko‘plab joylar mavjud bo‘lib, ularning aksariyati turizm infratuzilmasini rivojlantirishga asos bo‘ladi.

Xususan, Qoraqalpog‘istondagi insoniyat tamaddunidan hikoya qiluvchi arxeologik yodgorliklar bisyor. Hozirgi kunda Qoraqalpog‘istonda 300 dan ortiq arxeologik obyektlar mavjud bo‘lib, ulardan eng mashhurlari – Ko‘hna Urganch, Tupraqal‘a, Ellikqal‘a va Ayoqal‘a hududlaridagi qadimiy manzillardir. Bular, o‘z navbatida, sayyohlar uchun jozibadorlikni oshirib, hududning turistik imkoniyatlarini kengaytiradi.

Anjumanda uchta asosiy yo‘nalish bo‘yicha muhokamalar o‘tkazildi. Birinchi yo‘nalish Qoraqalpog‘istonda turizmni rivojlantirish tendensiyalariga bag‘ishlanib, mahalliy infratuzilmalarni takomillashtirish hamda turizm xizmatlarini kengaytirish bo‘yicha takliflar ishlab chiqildi. Ikkinchi yo‘nalishda etnografik turizmni rivojlantirish, xususan, mahalliy hunarmandchilikni targ‘ib etish va milliy madaniy boyliklarni namoyish qilish masalalari muhokama qilindi. Uchinchi yo‘nalish Qoraqalpog‘istonning ekologik turizm salohiyatini jahon turizm bozorida zamonaviy marketing strategiyalari orqali targ‘ib qilish masalalariga bag‘ishlandi.

Ushbu anjuman va uning natijalari Qoraqalpog‘iston Respublikasida turizmni rivojlantirish yo‘lida muhim qadamdir. Turizm, madaniy meros va ekologik yo‘nalishlar bo‘yicha ishlab chiqilgan taklif va tavsiyalar hududni xalqaro turistik xaritada o‘z o‘rniga ega bo‘lishiga yordam beradi.

Qoraqalpog‘iston Respublikasi tarixiy, madaniy va tabiiy boyliklarga ega hudud sifatida nafaqat O‘zbekiston, balki butun Markaziy Osiyoda alohida o‘rin tutadi. Bu hududni «ochiq osmon ostidagi arxeologik muzey» deb atash mumkin, chunki bu yerda qadimiy Xorazm madaniyatining markazi bo‘lgan Qoraqalpog‘istonda nafaqat arxeologik meros, balki etnografik va ekologik turizmni rivojlantirish uchun katta imkoniyatlar mavjud.

Qoraqalpog‘istonda o‘tkaziladigan «Madaniy xabardorlikni oshirish va ekologik barqaror turizmni rivojlantirish» mavzusidagi xalqaro anjuman ana

shunday salohiyatni namoyon etish va rivojlantirish maqsadida tashkil etilgan. Anjuman doirasida turli olimlar, tadqiqotchilar va xalqaro ekspertlar ishtirokida ekologik barqarorlik va madaniy merosni saqlash masalalari muhokama qilinib, zamonaviy turizm yo‘nalishlaridagi ilmiy-nazariy takliflar ishlab chiqildi.

Anjumanda uchta asosiy yo‘nalish bo‘yicha quyidagi muhokamalar o‘tkazildi:

- *Qoraqalpog‘iston Respublikasida turizmni rivojlantirish tendensiyalari;*
- *Etnografik turizmni tashkil etishning asosiy xususiyatlari;*
- *Qoraqalpog‘istonning ekologik turizm salohiyatini jahon turizm bozorida targ‘ib qilishning zamonaviy marketing strategiyalari.*

Anjuman va uning natijalari Qoraqalpog‘iston Respublikasida ekologik va etnografik turizm nafaqat hududning iqtisodiy rivojlanishiga, balki madaniy merosini saqlash va dunyoga tanitishga yordam berishi olgari surildi.

Anjumanda xalqaro institutlar vakillarining qatnashishi bejiz emas. Qoraqalpog‘istonning boy tarixi va Xorazm madaniyati bilan bog‘liq bo‘lgan qadimiy yodgorliklar va arxeologik topinmalar bu hududni nafaqat tarixchilar, arxeologlar uchun, balki turistlar uchun ham jozibadorligini oshirib boradi.

Masalan, Ko‘kcha III qabristoni – qadimgi bronza davri madaniyatiga oid yodgorlik bo‘lib, millioddan avvalgi XIII-XI asrlarga oid, deb taxmin qilinadi. Bu madaniyatlar ko‘p asrlar davomida bir-biri bilan hamkorlikda yashaganini va turli etnik guruhlarning madaniy merosini o‘zida mujassam etganini ko‘rsatadi.

Masalan, S.P. Tolstov¹ tomonidan o‘rganilgan Tazabagyab madaniyatlari ham Qoraqalpog‘istonning arxeologik salohiyatining muhim qismi bo‘lib, ularni o‘rganish natijasida bronza davrining ikki madaniyati bir vaqtning o‘zida mavjud bo‘lgani ma‘lum bo‘lgan. Bu esa hududda turli tarixiy etnik va madaniy jarayonlar sodir bo‘lganidan dalolat beradi.

Qoraqalpog‘istonning ushbu yodgorliklari va arxeologik manzillari sayyohlar uchun jozibadorlikni oshirishi mumkin.

Qoraqalpog‘iston Respublikasining turizm salohiyati juda katta bo‘lib, uni jahon turizm bozoriga zamonaviy marketing vositalari orqali chiqarish imkoni bor. Bu borada ekologik va etnografik turizm muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Ushbu turizm yo‘nalishlari nafaqat hududning iqtisodiy rivojlanishiga, balki uning madaniy merosini saqlash va dunyoga yoyishda ahamiyat kasb etadi.

Mazkur anjuman, ayniqsa, Qoraqalpog‘istonning kelgusi turizm salohiyatini mustahkamlashda, asosiy yo‘nalishlar bo‘yicha ishlab chiqilgan takliflarni keng tatbiq qilishda omil bo‘lib, mahalliy hunarmandchilikni rivojlantirish va yangi turizm xizmatlarini joriy qilishga, hudud aholisi uchun yetarli darajada doimiy va mavsumiy daromadli ish o‘rinlari yaratishga xizmat qiladi.

1 <https://ensiklopediya.uz>

II-SHO'BA

Etnografik turizmni
tashkil etishning
asosiy xususiyatlari

ECOTOURISM AS A NATURAL SOURCE OF INSPIRATION FOR ART AND CREATIVITY

Leora Eisenberg

Researcher at Harvard University, USA

The opening anecdote of my dissertation proposal was the story of how the famous pop band Yalla's song «Uchkuduk» was written – about how when in 1981, the legendary group drove through the small uranium-mining town, songwriter Yurii Entin allegedly wrote the song within 40 minutes. I won't bore you with that story here – everyone already knows it. But what you might now know is that everyone who read my dissertation proposal began to hum the song. The entire History Department at Harvard had heard it by late January 2024, and my father – who is from Canada – now regularly listens to it on its own. I recently created two different playlists of Central Asian music for my students and my colleagues, including an overwhelming number of songs from Uzbekistan, to great success. At work, my colleagues office love to comment that I've «created a monster.» No one can stop listening to Uzbek music. Indeed, it seems like Uzbekistan has created this most beautiful of monsters. Its many peoples – Uzbeks, Karakalpaks,

Tajiks, Russians, Kazakhs, and others – have rich traditions of music and dance that deserve attention. I believe that these cultures are one of many paths -- alongside eco-tourism, of course – that will promote tourism to this country that I have come to love so much.

There's actually a precedent for this, which I uncover in my dissertation. In 1925, Uzbekistan was well-represented at the International Exhibition of Decorative Arts in Paris by members of the Ethnographic Ensemble of Muhitdin Qoriyokubov, where the famed dancer Isadora Duncan allegedly asked to count Tamara Khanum's vertebrae, as she was convinced that the dancer would not have otherwise been able to perform dances like «Pilla.» In 1935, we saw something similar in London: Tamara Khanum, along with Usto Olim Komilov and Tukhtasin Jalilov, performed there, with Komilov even receiving a special medal from Queen Mary. American journalists and cultural figures, such as the journalist Anna Louise Strong and writer Langston Hughes, both visited Uzbekistan in

the 1920s and 30s and commented on the beauty of local music and dance. This tradition of cultural promotion through the national music and dances of Uzbekistan continued throughout the 20th century: musicians and dancers traveled far and wide, from doira player Avner Barayev's trips to India, Egypt, and Syria in the mid-1950s to the Aiqulash State Ensemble of Karakalpak Song and Dance's trip to Siberia and the Far East in the late 1980 s, to Yalla's two performances in Morocco in the late 1980s. The various music and dances of Uzbekistan have been promoting the country for about one hundred years at this point.

Uzbekistan is now well-placed to follow in its 20th-century footsteps. With the development of tourism to such cities as Bukhara, Khiva, Samarkand, and Nukus, thousands of people from across the globe come to admire Uzbekistan's architectural marvels, enjoy its spectacular nature, and try delicious foods, from plov (my favorite) and sumalak to beshbarmak and ak saulak. My father, who has nothing to do with Central Asia by blood or by work, has visited twice (both in 2022 and 2023) and will visit again this coming June. When visiting Uzbekistan for the first time in 2022, I met some French tourists at an AirBnB in Bukhara, and we are friends to this day. Also enchanted by Uzbekistan, they come back every year.

To be quite honest, though, the local cultures of Uzbekistan are not on all tourists' itineraries. Part of this is because in the summer, the time of year when the greatest number of tourists is able to come, is when theaters are frequently closed – and when the weather is warmest. But part of this is simply because the infrastructure is still in gestation. There are some very heartening developments, however: the recently reconstituted Bahor Ensemble, for example, has been travelling across the world and earning a name for itself, from China to the United States to Dubai. April saw the International Lyazgi Festival in Khorezm, dedicated to the art of this mesmerizingly beautiful dance, drawing several hundred participants from Brasil, France, Egypt, and Japan, alongside, of course, Uzbekistan and its Central Asian neighbors. London hosted the Uzbek Cultural Festival in June 2023, which brought Uzbek music and dance to the residents of one of the most dynamic and vibrant cities of the world. All these phenomena are helping others to acquaint themselves with and visit Uzbekistan.

But there is still so much more to do. Tourists come to Turkey to see dervishes spin; travelers flock to Milan to hear the opera; and people have long journeyed to Argentina – my long-held dream – to dance the tango. Why should Uzbekistan be any different? There is a well-known Russian-language expression about what it means to achieve happiness in this life: «to see Paris and die.» While I wish, of course, all tourists and visitors (myself included) a long, healthy life, perhaps we could work together to remake this slogan a la Uzbekistan: «to see Nukus and sing,» «to see Bukhara and

dance,» or, in my favorite rendition, «to see Uzbekistan and be amazed», just as I have been for the last two years. Yes, it's only been two years since my first visit to Uzbekistan!

For one, I propose the creation of special cultural tours to Uzbekistan. «Thematic» tourism has become increasingly popular: food tourism, eco-tourism, religious tourism, and more. So why not create specialized tours for culture, highlighting, for example, the unique songs and dances of the various regions of Uzbekistan? One could listen to kosiks and dastans in Nukus, watch the lyazgi in Khorezm, and watch Mukhtar Ashrafi's «The Amulet of Love» opera at the Theater of Opera and Ballet in Tashkent. This would not mean forgoing trips to the Savitsky Museum, the Registan Square, or the Tashkent metro (one of tourists' favorite spots) – it would mean incorporating them into a trip that allows visitors to see a side of Uzbekistan so incredible that I'm devoting my dissertation to it – but that has not yet received the attention that it deserves.

I also wonder if the summertime cultural infrastructure could be strengthened to accommodate the flows of tourists. While I was thrilled to see that the Lyazgi Festival, for example, was taking place in April 2024, I knew that many would have to miss it because it was a little too early for university employees and students, like myself, to attend. While I realize that theaters do not work year-round, I wonder if Tashkent, Nukus, and Samarkand could organize music or dance festivals meant for youth? I know that this has already begun, as with the Stikhila Festival in Kzylkum in 2023 and Munak in 2024, which is terrific. I think, though, that this could be on a much larger

scale -- and more specifically about national culture. Neighboring Almaty has long been known as «the city of summer musical festivals,» which draw youth (and performers!) from across the world. What's important to note is that this is not just for specialists – this is for amateurs, fans, and regular people like you and me. Tashkent has an equally vibrant cultural scene, as well as the infrastructure (concert halls, performance venues, etc.) to do the same. I will be thrilled to be involved in the development of such international events not least because I am the world's biggest fan of Uzbek music and dance, but also because I am personally invested in Uzbekistan's development.

In fact, I have come to call Uzbekistan my «Disneyland,» because, like Disneyland's motto, it has become my «happiest place on earth.» I tell everyone that there's no place quite like it and beg my friends to visit me. I've hardly been to a place with kinder people, more beautiful songs, more enchanting dances, and more delicious food. I have never had to worry about where I can stay or wonder if I'll have enough to eat. Equally importantly, I also enjoy the variety of experiences one can have here: from learning about yurtmaking crafts in Karakalpakstan, as I'm doing here for the first time, dancing at the Kazakh wedding I attended in Yangiyul to the interviews I've conducted with former dancers of the Bahor Ensemble in Tashkent. Perhaps more than anything else, I want as many people as possible to come to know the many cultures of Uzbekistan which I have come to love. I've begun this work by getting my colleagues to sing Uchkuduk with me – and I hope that we can continue this task together by promoting the many national cultures of Uzbekistan.

Qoraqalpog'iston turizm infratuzilmasi
Туристическая инфраструктура Каракалпакстана
Tourism infrastructure of Karakalpakstan

Qoraqalpog'iston turizm infratuzilmasi
Туристическая инфраструктура Каракалпакстана
Tourism infrastructure of Karakalpakstan

Qoraqalpog'iston turizm infratuzilmasi
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Tourism infrastructure of Karakalpakstan

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